

Exploring New Frontiers in Numerical Root-Finding: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

A primary challenge in computer mathematics is identifying the roots of nonlinear functions. This paper examines and compares the two-line approach, an extension of the secant method, a generalization of the bisection method, an extension of the Newton-Raphson algorithm, the Perpendicular method, an MVT-based algorithm, and several other root-finding methods. To assess these strategies, we examine the number of iterations needed and the accuracy of the approximate roots. The findings indicate that the Extension of the Secant approach consistently yields optimal outcomes with few iterations for functions exhibiting rapid behavioral changes. Additional repetitions are typically required for the extension of the Newton-Raphson method to get equivalent precision. The inability of analogous approaches such as Parallel to converge for specific functions illustrates their limitations. This comparative analysis elucidates the effectiveness and applicability of several approaches across diverse activities.

Keywords: Root, Mean Value Theorem (MVT) based method, Perpendicular method, Two straight lines method, Generalization of Bisection method, Mean formula based method, K-section method, Extension of secant method, Parallel method, Extension of Newton-Raphson method.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of mathematics's oldest tasks is finding the roots of polynomials. Finding roots for an equation is always an interesting topic for researchers. Early Middle Age Arab academics, Omar Khayyam being the most well-known, were proficient in the solution to quadratic equations. In the mid-16th century, G. Cardano first resolved the cubic equation in closed form, followed by the quadratic equation shortly thereafter. N.H. Abel established in the early 19th century that polynomials of degree five or higher cannot be resolved using a formula derived from their coefficients, in contrast to polynomials of degree four or lower. Researchers have subsequently concentrated on numerical (iterative) methods, notably Newton's method from the 17th century and Bernoulli's from the 18th century. The bisection method is one of the oldest and simplest numerical techniques for determining roots. It's based on the application of intermediate value property repeatedly[1, 2]. Vrahatis and Iordanidis [3] mentioned a rapid generalized method of bisection method. Generalization for higher dimensions discussed by Wood [4]. Novak *et al.* [5] introduced the hybrid Secant-Bisection method. An effective modified algorithm of the Bisection method with asymptotic convergence given by Xinyuan Wu [6]. Gutierrez *et al.* [7] analyzed the complexity of the Bisection method and Yakoubsohn [8] used the Bisection-Exclusion method of univariate analytic functions. To accelerate the bisection technique while maintaining its

guaranteed convergence and a higher order of convergence than the bisection method, the Regula-Falsi approach utilized the straight-line notion. Dowell and Jarratt improved the Regula-Falsi method in 1971 by substituting the old function with an intermediate function. Compared with the earlier Regula-Falsi Method, they achieved more effective convergence [9].

False position method based on homotopy analysis method (HAM) studied by Saeid and Liao [10] Wu and Wu used Steffensen's method to find quadratic convergent algorithm and generate a new root-finding way [11]. A free derivative iteration method of order three studied by Zhu and Wu [12]. Newton-Raphson method has second-order accuracy, it converges more rapidly than the above-all method. But, it fails when the tangent becomes parallel to the x-axis. Moreover, it may not always guarantee the root. The sufficient condition for converging the roots by the Newton-Raphson method was studied by Johan and Ronald. They also introduced some other functions to replace the first derivative function [13]. In place of the Newton-Raphson approach, Kanwar et al. propose an alternative iterative method with quadratic convergence [14]. Additionally, he developed third-order iterative techniques for nonlinear equations. They have provided third-order multi-point solutions using the previous concept without the need for a second derivative [15].

Sharma and Goyal [16] attempted to address the fourth-order derivative-free method employing Steffensen's technique, utilizing forward and backward difference approaches categorized as one-step and two-step ways. Noor and Ahmad [17] presented the predictor-corrector method employing the conventional Regula Falsi strategy, which produced enhanced outcomes relative to prior methods. Noor et al. [18] subsequently suggested and examined many two-step methods for solving non-linear equations. They then introduced a three-step iterative method demonstrating third-order convergence. Chen and Li [19] presented an enhanced exponential Regula-Falsi approach for addressing non-linear equations. In their proposed method, they accelerate the conveyance by applying an exponential iterative method [20]. Descartes's method is provided by Sagraloff and Mehlhorn [21] for computing the roots of polynomial equations. This method yields accurate estimates of the polynomial coefficients. The implementation of isolating intervals to arbitrary small sizes may likewise apply to their algorithm. Abbott [22] introduced refined quadratic intervals for real roots. It is not necessary to evaluate the derivatives when using this superb algorithm.

II. FLOW CHARTS AND ALGORITHMS

Figure 1: Flow charts for the Perpendicular, MVT-Based, Two Straight Lines and Generalization of Bisection Method

Figure 2: Flow chart for the Parallel and Extension of Newton Raphson Method

Algorithm of Perpendicular Method, MVT-Based Method, Two straight Lines Method, Generalization of Bisection Method, Root Finding Using Mean Formula, K-Section Method, Extension of Secant Method and Extension of Newton Raphson Method:

Step 1: Take input a, b such that $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$

Step 2: Calculate the following for each method, respectively:

Perpendicular method: $x = \frac{c_2 - c_1}{m_1 - m_2}$

MVT Based Method: Solve the equation $f'(x) = m$ for c

Two Straight-Lines Method: $x = \frac{a m_1 - b m_2}{m_1 - m_2}$, where m_1 and m_2 are the slopes of the two straight lines.

Generalization of Bisection Method: $x = a + \frac{1}{n}(b - a)$; $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1, 2\}$; where $a < b$

Root Finding Using Mean Formula:

Weighted Mean (with $w_1 > 0$ and $w_2 > 0$): $\frac{w_1 a + w_2 b}{w_1 + w_2}$

Geometric Mean (GM): $\sqrt{a \times b}$, where a and b are nonzero and both have same sign.

Harmonic Mean (HM): $\frac{2ab}{a + b}$

Quadratic Mean (QM)/RMS: $\sqrt{\frac{a^2 + b^2}{2}}$

K-Section Method: Solve the equation $x = \frac{a+b}{k}$, where k is an element of $(1 + \frac{a}{b}, 1 + \frac{b}{a})$ where none of a or b exactly equal to 0.

Extension of Secant Method: $g(x) = g(a) - \frac{f(a)}{m_1}$, where $m_1 = \frac{f(a) - f(b)}{g(a) - g(b)}$

Step 3: If $f(a) \times f(x) > 0$, set $a = x$, otherwise $b = x$

Step 4: If $|f(x)| < tol$ then stop; otherwise, go to Step 2

Algorithm of Parallel and Extension of Newton Raphson Method

Step 1: Take input x_0

Step 2: Calculate the following for each method, respectively:

Parallel Method: $x_1 = x_0 - \frac{f(x_0)}{m}$

Extension of Newton Raphson Method: $g(x_1) = g(x_0) - \frac{g'(x_0) f(x_0)}{f'(x_0)}$

where, $g(x)$ is any continuous function. We prefer $g(x_0) = x^n$, where n is an odd integer.

Step 3: Set $x_0 = x_1$

Step 4: If $|f(x_0)| < tol$ then Stop otherwise, go to Step 2

III. DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES OF ROOT FINDING

Perpendicular Method:

Theorem: Let us consider the function $f(x) = 0$ which is continuous on $[a, b]$ and $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$. We consider two perpendicular straight lines, one passes through $(a, f(a))$ and $(b, f(b))$ and another is perpendicular to the first line and passes through $(b, 0)$. Then the perpendicular method generates a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ which converges linearly.

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = \frac{(\alpha - f'(\alpha))}{\left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right)}$$

According to states above, the straight lines are

$$y - f(a) = \frac{f(a)-f(b)}{b-a}(x - a) \text{ and } y = -\frac{b-a}{f(a)-f(b)}(x - b)$$

Those can be written as follows:

$$a_1x + y + c_1 = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$a_2x + y + c_2 = 0 \quad (1b)$$

where $a_1 = -\frac{f(a)-f(b)}{b-a} = -m$, $a_2 = -\frac{1}{a_1} = \frac{1}{m}$, $c_1 = -a \times a_1 - f(a) = a \times m - f(a)$ and $c_2 = \frac{b}{a_1} = -\frac{b}{m}$. From (1a) and (1b), we get

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{c_2 - c_1}{a_1 - a_2} \\ \therefore x &= \frac{-\frac{b}{m} - am + f(a)}{-m - \frac{1}{m}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If $a = \alpha + e_i$ and $b = \alpha + e_{i-1}$, where α is the exact root, i.e. $x = \alpha + e_{i+1}$ then (2) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha + e_{i+1} &= \frac{m(\alpha + e_i) + \frac{\alpha + e_{i-1}}{m} - f(\alpha + e_i)}{m + \frac{1}{m}} \\ \Rightarrow m\alpha + \frac{\alpha}{m} + e_{i+1} \left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right) &= m\alpha + e_i\alpha + \frac{\alpha}{m} + \frac{e_{i-1}}{m} - f(\alpha + e_i) \\ \therefore e_{i+1} \left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right) &= e_i\alpha + \frac{e_{i-1}}{m} - f(\alpha + e_i) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

From Taylor series $f(\alpha + e_i) = f(\alpha) + \frac{e_i}{1!}f'(\alpha) + \frac{e_i^2}{2!}f''(\alpha) + \dots = \frac{e_i}{1!}f'(\alpha)$, neglecting the higher order terms. Now from (3)

$$\begin{aligned} e_{i+1} \left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right) &= e_i\alpha + \frac{e_{i-1}}{m} - \frac{e_i}{1!}f'(\alpha) \\ \Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} \left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right) &= (\alpha - f'(\alpha)) + \frac{e_{i-1}}{m e_i} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{(\alpha - f'(\alpha))}{\left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right)} + \frac{e_{i-1}}{m \left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right) e_i} \\ \therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{(\alpha - f'(\alpha))}{\left(m + \frac{1}{m}\right)} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: Graphical representation of Perpendicular Method

MVT-Based Method:

Theorem: Let $f(x) \in C[a, b]$ and $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$, then MVT theorem generates a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ produced by the iterative formula that is linearly convergent.

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = 1$$

In this method, we use the concept of the fundamental mean value theorem, slightly modified to solve the equation of the form $f(x) = 0$. The process involves finding a suitable interval $[a, b]$ in a real number line such that the function has a root within the interval. After choosing the desired interval, we calculate the slope of a straight line passing through two points $(a, f(a))$ and $(b, f(b))$ which is $m = \frac{f(a) - f(b)}{a - b}$. Then we set $f'(x) = m$, now two branches can be produced based on the linearity of $f'(x)$. If $f'(x)$ is in such a form that we can express explicitly x equal to something, which will be the iterative formula to find the root of $f(x) = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} f'(x_i) &= \frac{f(a) - f(b)}{a - b} = m_1 \\ \Rightarrow f'(\alpha + e_i) &= m_1 \quad [\text{considering } x_i = \alpha + e_i] \\ \therefore f'(\alpha) + \frac{e_i}{1!} f''(\alpha) + \frac{e_i^2}{2!} f'''(\alpha) + \dots &= m_1 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, for the next consecutive iteration, $f'(\alpha) + \frac{e_{i+1}}{1!}f''(\alpha) + \frac{e_{i+2}^2}{2!}f'''(\alpha) + \dots = m_2$

From the above two equations, we get

$$(e_{i+1} - e_i) f'(\alpha) + \frac{1}{2!} (e_{i+1}^2 - e_i^2) f''(\alpha) + \dots = m_2 - m_1$$

$$\Rightarrow (e_{i+1} - e_i) f'(\alpha) = m_2 - m_1 \text{ [neglecting the higher powers of error terms]}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} - 1 = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{e_i}$$

when the length of the interval is sufficiently small then $m_2 - m_1 = 0$

$$\therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = 1 \quad (4)$$

Now we explicitly express $f'(x) = m$ to make x equal to something by the following example.

Example: Let, $f(x) = x - \cos x$, then $f'(x) = m$ gives $x = \sin^{-1}(m - 1)$, where m is the slope of the secant line.

Figure 4: Graphical representation of MVT-Based Method

Two Straight-Lines Method:

Theorem: Suppose that $f(x) \in C[a, b]$ and $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$, then the two straight-lines method generates a sequence, $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ which satisfy the following condition

$$|x_n - x_0| \leq \frac{|a - b|}{\left| \left(\frac{m}{k_2} \right)^n \right|}; \text{ where } x_0 \text{ is the exact root.}$$

First, consider two straight lines: one passing through the point $(a, 0)$ and the other passing through $(b, 0)$. The slope of the first straight line is $m_1 = \tan \theta$ while the other one slope is $m_2 = \tan(90 + \alpha) = -\cot \alpha$; $0 < \theta < 90$, $0 < \alpha < 90$. If the slope of a straight line is less than 90 degree and another straight line's slope is greater than 90 degree, then the abscissa of their intersecting point must be in $[a, b]$. The lines passing through $(a, 0)$ and $(b, 0)$, respectively, are:

$$L_1 : y = m_1(x - a)$$

$$L_2 : y = m_2(x - b)$$

where m_1 is the slope of first line and m_2 is slope of second line. The abscissa of the intersecting point between L_1 and L_2 is

$$x = \frac{am_1 - bm_2}{m_1 - m_2}$$

Here, a and b are the initial guess and

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{am_1 - bm_2}{m_1 - m_2} \\ x &= \frac{am_2 - bm_2 + ak}{k}, \quad m_1 - m_2 = k \\ x &= a + \frac{(a - b)m_2}{k} \end{aligned}$$

After 1st iteration length between $[x, a] = \frac{(a-b)m_2}{k}$ and after 2nd iteration length between $[x, a] = \frac{(a-b)m_2^2}{k^2}$. Similarly after n^{th} iteration length between $[a, b] = \frac{(a-b)m_2^n}{k^n}$.

Generalization of Bisection Method:

Theorem: Let $f(x) \in C[a, b]$ if $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$, then the generalization of the bisection method generates a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ which converges linearly,

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = 1 - \frac{1}{n}$$

Let $x = a + \frac{1}{n}(b - a)$, where $n \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $n > 1$, which is the famous formula for generating a random number between two numbers. Clearly, x is bounded by a and b , also we will get

Figure 5: Graphical representation of Two Straight-Lines Method

at least one x that satisfies $f(x) = 0$. Now form $x = a + \frac{1}{n}(b - a)$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= \alpha + e_{i+1} = \alpha + e_i + \frac{1}{n}(e_{i-1} - e_i) \quad \left[\begin{array}{l} \bar{x} = \alpha + e_{i+1} \\ a = \alpha + e_i \\ b = \alpha + e_{i-1} \end{array} \right] \\
 \Rightarrow (e_{i+1} - e_i) &= \frac{1}{n}(e_{i-1} - e_i) \\
 \Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} - 1 &= \frac{1}{n} \left[\frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i} - 1 \right] \\
 \Rightarrow \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} 1 - \frac{1}{n} \quad \left[\text{since, } \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i} \rightarrow 0 \right] \\
 \therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= 1 - \frac{1}{n}
 \end{aligned}$$

Root Finding Using Mean Formula:

Theorem: Let $f(x) \in C[a, b]$, if $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$ then the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ will be found from the mean formula (Quadratic mean, Geometric mean, Harmonic mean) which is

linearly convergent

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = \frac{1}{2}$$

And, for the weighted mean formula

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = \frac{w_1}{w_1 + w_2}$$

Proof: Considering $x = \alpha + e_{i+1}$, $a = \alpha + e_i$, $b = \alpha + e_{i-1}$, where α be the exact root, e_i be the error term in i^{th} iteration step. Now we can write,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{aw_1 + bw_2}{w_1 + w_2}; \quad \forall w_1, w_2 > 0 \\ \Rightarrow \alpha + e_{i+1} &= \frac{(\alpha + e_i)w_1 + (\alpha + e_{i-1})w_2}{w_1 + w_2} \\ \Rightarrow \alpha(w_1 + w_2) + e_{i+1}(w_1 + w_2) &= \alpha(w_1 + w_2) + e_i w_1 + e_{i-1} w_2 \\ \Rightarrow e_{i+1}(w_1 + w_2) &= e_i w_1 + e_{i-1} w_2 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{e_i w_1}{(w_1 + w_2) e_i} + \frac{e_{i-1} w_2}{e_i} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{w_1}{(w_1 + w_2)} + \frac{e_{i-1} w_2}{e_i} \\ \therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{w_1}{w_1 + w_2} \left[\because \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i} \rightarrow 0 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Again, consider $x = \sqrt{a \times b}$, where, $a, b > 0$ and $x = -\sqrt{a \times b}$, where, $a, b < 0$. From these, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 &= a \times b, \quad \text{where } a \text{ and } b \text{ both have same sign.} \\ \Rightarrow (\alpha + e_{i+1})^2 &= (\alpha + e_i) \times (\alpha + e_{i-1}) \\ \Rightarrow \alpha^2 + e_{i+1}^2 + 2\alpha e_{i+1} &= \alpha^2 + (e_i + e_{i-1})\alpha + e_i e_{i-1} \\ \Rightarrow e_{i+1}^2 + 2\alpha e_{i+1} &= (e_i + e_{i-1})\alpha + e_i e_{i-1} \\ \Rightarrow 2e_{i+1} &= (e_i + e_{i-1}) \quad [\because \text{errors are very small}] \\ \Rightarrow 2 \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= 1 + \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i} \\ \therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\because \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i} \rightarrow 0 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Again consider

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= \sqrt{\frac{a^2 + b^2}{2}} \quad \text{or} \quad -\sqrt{\frac{a^2 + b^2}{2}} \quad \text{where } a \text{ and } b \text{ both have same sign.} \\
\Rightarrow x^2 &= \frac{a^2 + b^2}{2} \\
\Rightarrow 2(\alpha + e_{i+1})^2 &= (\alpha + e_i)^2 + (\alpha + e_{i-1})^2 \\
\Rightarrow 4\alpha e_{i+1} + 2e_{i+1}^2 &= 2\alpha(e_i + e_{i-1}) + e_i^2 + e_{i-1}^2 \\
\Rightarrow e_{i+1} &= \frac{1}{2}(e_i + e_{i-1}) \quad [\because \text{errors are very small}] \\
\Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i}\right) \\
\Rightarrow \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{1}{2} \quad \left[\because \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i} \rightarrow 0\right] \tag{7}
\end{aligned}$$

Again, consider that x is the harmonic mean of a and b , that is

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= \frac{2ab}{a+b} \\
\Rightarrow \alpha + e_{i+1} &= \frac{2(\alpha + e_i)(\alpha + e_{i-1})}{\alpha + e_i + \alpha + e_{i-1}} \\
\Rightarrow \alpha + e_{i+1} &= \frac{2\alpha^2 + 2(e_i + e_{i-1})\alpha + 2e_i e_{i-1}}{2\alpha + e_i + e_{i-1}} \\
\Rightarrow e_{i+1} &= \frac{1}{2}(e_i + e_{i-1}) \quad [\because \text{errors are very small}] \\
\Rightarrow \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= \frac{1}{2} \quad \left[\because \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i} \rightarrow 0\right] \tag{8}
\end{aligned}$$

Let the root of the function $f(x)$ bounded through $[a, b]$, then in any of the loop $x = \frac{a^n + b^n}{k}$ is the updated root.

$$\begin{aligned}
a &< \frac{a^n + b^n}{k} < b \\
\frac{a^n + b^n}{b} &< k < \frac{a^n + b^n}{a}
\end{aligned}$$

Let $k = \min\left(\frac{a^n + b^n}{a}, \frac{a^n + b^n}{b}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{a^n + b^n}{a} - \frac{a^n + b^n}{b}\right)$.

If $\min\left(\frac{a^n + b^n}{a}, \frac{a^n + b^n}{b}\right) = \frac{a^n + b^n}{b}$.

So, $k = \frac{a^n + b^n}{b} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{a^n + b^n}{a} - \frac{a^n + b^n}{b}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{a^n + b^n}{a} + \frac{a^n + b^n}{b}\right)$.

Then, $x = \frac{a^n + b^n}{k} = \frac{(a^n + b^n)}{\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b}\right) \times (a^n + b^n)} = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b}} = \frac{2ab}{a+b}$.

Now $x = \frac{2ab}{a+b}$ and together with the Intermediate value theorem, we can find the root of any function which is continuous on $[a, b]$ and $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$.

K-Section Method:

$$\begin{aligned}x &= \frac{a+b}{k} \\a &< \frac{a+b}{k} < b \\ \frac{a+b}{b} &< k < \frac{a+b}{a} \\ 1 + \frac{a}{b} &< k < 1 + \frac{b}{a}\end{aligned}$$

If $k \in \left(1 + \frac{a}{b}, 1 + \frac{b}{a}\right)$, then it must converge to the root, where $x = \frac{a+b}{k}$ and together with the Intermediate value theorem, we can find the root of any function which is continuous on $[a, b]$ and $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$, where none of a or b exactly equal to 0.

Extension of Secant Method:

Theorem: Let us consider the function $f(x) = 0$ which is continuous on $[x_0, x_1]$ and $f(x_0) \times f(x_1) < 0$. Then the extension of secant method generates a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ which is linearly convergent.

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|(x_{i+1} - x_i)|}{|(x_i - x_{i-1})|} = 1$$

We know for secant method $x = x_0 - \frac{f(x_0)}{m}$, where $m = \frac{f(x_0) - f(x_1)}{x_0 - x_1}$. And the straight line passing through $(x_0, f(x_0))$ and $(x_1, f(x_1))$ is $y = m(x - x_0) + f(x_0)$. If we think a curve passing through $(g(x_0), f(x_0))$ and $(g(x_1), f(x_1))$, then $g(x) = g(x_0) - \frac{f(x_0)}{m_1}$, where $m_1 = \frac{f(x_0) - f(x_1)}{g(x_0) - g(x_1)}$.

For example suppose $g(x)$ has the form x^n , where n is any positive integer but its odd value is preferable. We know $x^n = k$ has n roots but here we are thinking about only real roots bounded by x_0 and x_1 . The readers can choose $g(x)$ in any form.

Considering $x_i = \alpha + e_i$, where α is the exact root and e_i is the error of i^{th} term. Using Taylor's theorem and neglecting the higher power of error terms we can write $f(\alpha + e_i) = e_i f'(\alpha)$, $f(\alpha + e_{i-1}) = e_{i-1} f'(\alpha)$, $g(\alpha + e_i) = (\alpha + e_i)^n = \alpha^n + n \alpha^{n-1} e_i$, $g(\alpha + e_{i-1}) = (\alpha + e_{i-1})^n = \alpha^n + n \alpha^{n-1} e_{i-1}$, and $g(\alpha + e_{i+1}) = (\alpha + e_{i+1})^n = \alpha^n + n \alpha^{n-1} e_{i+1}$. Now the iterative formula of $g(x)$ gives

$$\begin{aligned}g(x_{i+1}) &= g(x_i) - \frac{f(x_i)}{\frac{f(x_i) - f(x_{i-1})}{g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})}} \\ \Rightarrow g(x_{i+1}) - g(x_i) &= \frac{-f(x_i) [g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})]}{f(x_i) - f(x_{i-1})} \\ \Rightarrow n \alpha^{n-1} (e_{i+1} - e_i) &= \frac{-e_i f'(\alpha) \times n \alpha^{n-1} (e_i - e_{i-1})}{e_i f'(\alpha) - e_{i-1} f'(\alpha)} \\ \Rightarrow |(e_{i+1} - e_i)| &= |-e_i| \\ \Rightarrow \frac{|(e_{i+1} - e_i)|}{|(e_i - e_{i-1})|} &= \frac{|-e_i|}{|(e_i - e_{i-1})|}\end{aligned}$$

Figure 6: Graphical representation of Extension of Secant Method

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Rightarrow \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|(e_{i+1} - e_i)|}{|(e_i - e_{i-1})|} = \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\left|(-1 + \frac{e_{i-1}}{e_i})\right|} \\
 &\Rightarrow \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|(e_{i+1} - e_i)|}{|(e_i - e_{i-1})|} = 1 \\
 &\therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|(x_{i+1} - x_i)|}{|(x_i - x_{i-1})|} = 1 \tag{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus (9) is the condition for the rate of convergence for the extension of the Secant method.

Parallel Method:

Theorem: Let $f(x) \in C[a, b]$ and $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$ then there exists a secant line with the finite value of the slope, m produce a linearly convergent sequence by the iterative formula.

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = 1 - \frac{f'(\alpha)}{m}$$

We consider two straight lines, one passes through $(a, f(a))$ and $(b, f(b))$ and the other is parallel to the first line. So the slope of both lines is $m = \frac{f(b)-f(a)}{b-a}$. If $x = a - \frac{f(a)}{m}$, where m is a nonzero constant, then there exists a secant line for which $f(x)$ is approximately close to 0. Suppose α be the exact root, e_i be the error term in i^{th} iteration step, then $x_{i+1} = \alpha + e_{i+1}$ and $x_i = \alpha + e_i$. Since $x = a - \frac{f(a)}{m}$, we can write, $x_{i+1} = x_i - \frac{f(x_i)}{m}$. Now we have the following:

Figure 7: Graphical representation of Parallel Method

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{i+1} - x_i &= e_{i+1} - e_i = \frac{-f(x_i)}{m} \\
\Rightarrow e_{i+1} - e_i &= \frac{-f(x_i)}{m} \\
\Rightarrow e_{i+1} - e_i &= \frac{-f(\alpha + e_i)}{m} \\
\Rightarrow e_{i+1} - e_i &= \frac{-\left[f(\alpha) + \frac{e_i}{1!} f'(\alpha) + \frac{e_i^2}{2!} f''(\alpha) + \dots \right]}{m} \\
\Rightarrow e_{i+1} - e_i &= \frac{-\frac{e_i}{1!} f'(\alpha) + 0}{m} \\
\Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} - 1 &= -\frac{f'(\alpha)}{m}; \text{ neglecting higher derivative terms} \\
\Rightarrow \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= 1 - \frac{f'(\alpha)}{m} \\
\therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} &= 1 - \frac{f'(\alpha)}{m}
\end{aligned}$$

Extension of Newton Raphson Method:

In Newton Raphson method we make a tangent in an initial guess $(x_0, f(x_0))$

$$y = \frac{df(x)}{dx} (x - x_0) + f(x_0)$$

If we make like a tangent line using any curve $g(x)$ then we have

$$y = \frac{df(x)}{dg(x)} (g(x) - g(x_0)) + f(x_0)$$

Along the x -axis,

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \frac{\frac{df(x)}{dx}}{\frac{dg(x)}{dx}} (g(x) - g(x_0)) + f(x_0) \\
\Rightarrow 0 &= \frac{f'(x_0)}{g'(x_0)} (g(x) - g(x_0)) + f(x_0)
\end{aligned}$$

i.e. at x_0

$$\begin{aligned}
y &= \frac{df(x_0)}{dg(x_0)} (g(x) - g(x_0)) + f(x_0) \\
\Rightarrow 0 &= \frac{\frac{df(x_0)}{dx}}{\frac{dg(x_0)}{dx}} (g(x) - g(x_0)) + f(x_0) \\
\Rightarrow 0 &= \frac{f'(x_0)}{g'(x_0)} (g(x) - g(x_0)) + f(x_0) \\
\Rightarrow g(x) &= g(x_0) - \frac{g'(x_0) f(x_0)}{f'(x_0)}
\end{aligned}$$

where, $g(x)$ is any continuous function. We prefer $g(x) = x^n$, where n is odd integer.

Figure 8: Graphical representation of Extension of Newton Raphson Method

Convergence of the extension of Newton Raphson method depends on the stability of the curve, $g(x)$ colored in yellow in Fig. 8 which is the formula of $g(x)$. We need to find where the derivative of $g(x)$ is equal to 0 to find the solution of $f(x)$.

Considering $g(x) = x^n$ and $x_i = \alpha + e_i$, where α is the exact root and e_i is the error of i^{th} term. Using Taylor's theorem and neglecting the higher power of error terms we can write, $f(\alpha + e_i) = e_i f'(\alpha)$, $f'(\alpha + e_i) = f'(\alpha) + e_i f''(\alpha)$, $g'(x_i) = nx_i^{n-1}$, $\Rightarrow g'(\alpha + e_i) = n(\alpha + e_i)^{n-1} = n(\alpha^{n-1} + (n-1)\alpha^{n-2}e_i)$, $g(\alpha + e_i) = (\alpha + e_i)^n = \alpha^n + n\alpha^{n-1}e_i$, and $g(\alpha +$

$e_{i+1}) = (\alpha + e_{i+1})^n = \alpha^n + n \alpha^{n-1} e_{i+1}$. Now the iterative formula of $g(x)$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} g(x_{i+1}) &= g(x_i) - \frac{g'(x_i) f(x_i)}{f'(x_i)} \\ \Rightarrow \alpha^n + n \alpha^{n-1} e_{i+1} &= \alpha^n + n \alpha^{n-1} e_i - \frac{n(\alpha^{n-1} + (n-1)\alpha^{n-2} e_i) \times e_i f'(\alpha)}{f'(\alpha) + e_i f''(\alpha)} \\ \Rightarrow \alpha^{n-1} (e_{i+1} - e_i) &= -\frac{(\alpha^{n-1} + (n-1)\alpha^{n-2} e_i) \times e_i f'(\alpha)}{f'(\alpha) + e_i f''(\alpha)} \\ \Rightarrow e_{i+1} f'(\alpha) + e_{i+1} e_i f''(\alpha) - e_i f'(\alpha) - e_i^2 f''(\alpha) &= -e_i f'(\alpha) - (n-1) \frac{1}{\alpha} e_i^2 f'(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow e_{i+1} f'(\alpha) + e_{i+1} e_i f''(\alpha) = e_i^2 \left(f''(\alpha) - (n-1) \frac{1}{\alpha} f'(\alpha) \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow f'(\alpha) \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i^2} + f''(\alpha) \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = f''(\alpha) - (n-1) \frac{1}{\alpha} f'(\alpha)$$

Equating the coefficients and taking limits we get

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i^2} = \frac{1-n}{\alpha} \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{e_{i+1}}{e_i} = 1 \quad (10)$$

Theorem: Let $f(x) \in C^1[a, b]$, $x \in (a, b)$ such that $f(x) = 0$ and $f'(x) \neq 0$, then the extension of Newton Raphson method generates a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ which is quadratically convergent.

Why those formulas converge to root?

1. The interval $[a, b]$ satisfies the condition $f(a) \times f(b) < 0$, and it satisfies the relation of the Intermediate value theorem. So there exists at least one point for which $f(x) = 0$.
2. As for each iteration satisfying quote 1, we must find a situation in an iteration for which there is only one point and in this situation also satisfy quote 1, so this point will be x for which $f(x) = 0$.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Table 1, which analyzes the function $f(x) = e^{\sin x} - x - 1$ throughout the interval $[1, 4]$, the Extension of Secant technique surpassed other methods by necessitating merely 4 iterations to estimate the root, achieving a minimal error of $|f(x_n)| = 0.0000045$. The Parallel approach and the Extension of the Newton-Raphson method completed 7 and 5 iterations, respectively, whereas other techniques, including the Generalization of Bisection and K-Section methods, necessitated much more iterations (14–20). Root finding using GM is one method that used mean formulas to reduce errors, but iterations were more numerous after that. Therefore, it is clear that mean-based methods are not necessarily the most efficient in terms of iteration count, even when they give adequate accuracy.

Table 2 examines the function $f(x) = x e^{-x} - 0.1$ over the interval $[0, 1]$, demonstrating that the Extension of the Secant approach achieved notable efficacy with merely 4 iterations. Nonetheless, the Extension of the Newton-Raphson approach attained the greatest precision,

diminishing $|f(x_n)|$ to 0.00000093, albeit requiring 35 iterations. The Generalization of the Bisection technique showed efficacy after 10 iterations, but the Parallel approach did not converge, demonstrating that certain methods may be inappropriate for particular functions. Ultimately, in Table 3, for the function $f(x) = 1 - 11x^{11}$ over the interval $[0.2, 1]$, the MVT-based approach necessitated 11 iterations and demonstrated commendable precision. The Perpendicular method encountered difficulties, requiring 43 iterations, but techniques such as Root discovery utilizing HM attained great accuracy in 18 iterations.

Table 1: Approximate roots of $f(x) = e^{\sin x} - x - 1$ on $[1, 4]$ with $tol=10^{-04}$

Method Name	Total Iteration taken	Approximate Root	$ f(x_n) $
Perpendicular	14	1.6967	0.0001226
MVT Based	14	1.69678	0.000038
Two straight lines	15	1.696840	0.000037
Generalization of Bisection	16	1.69678	0.000042
Root finding using GM	14	1.696801	0.0000152
Root finding using HM	14	1.69677	0.00026
Root finding using QM	15	1.696797	0.0000207
K-Section	20	1.696779	0.0000447
Extension of Secant	4	1.696808	0.0000045
Parallel	7	1.6967	0.00026
Extension of Newton Raphson	5	1.69683	0.000024

Table 2: Approximate roots of $f(x) = x e^{-x} - 0.1$ on $[0, 1]$ with $tol=10^{-04}$

Method Name	Total Iteration taken	Approximate Root	$ f(x_n) $
Perpendicular	24	0.111912	0.000063
MVT Based	11	0.11181	0.000012
Two straight lines	13	0.11193837	0.000084
Generalization of Bisection	10	0.11175464	0.000062
Root finding using GM	12	0.111711	0.0000966
Root finding using HM	26	0.1118279	0.000004
Root finding using QM	14	0.111858	0.0000202
K-Section	18	0.111802	0.0000247
Extension of Secant	4	0.11194549	0.000089
Parallel	Not converge for this equation		
Extension of Newton Raphson	5	0.1118159102	0.000013

Table 3: Approximate roots of $f(x) = 1 - 11x^{11}$ on $[0.2, 1]$ with $tol=10^{-04}$

Method Name	Total Iteration taken	Approximate Root	$ f(x_n) $
Perpendicular	43	0.804126	0.000084
MVT Based	15	0.804124	0.000092
Two straight lines	15	0.804134	0.000013
Generalization of Bisection	16	0.80412	0.000072
Root finding using GM	17	0.804134	0.00000813
Root finding using HM	18	0.80413257	0.000007
Root finding using QM	14	0.804128	0.0000761
K-Section	24	0.804128	0.0000684
Extension of Secant	29	0.80412797	0.00007
Parallel	11	0.804133	0.00011
Extension of Newton Raphson	35	0.804133166	0.00000093

CONCLUSION

Several root-finding algorithms were compared in this work. These algorithms ranged from adaptations of traditional methods like Secant and Newton-Raphson to more recent ones like the Perpendicular, MVT-based, and two straight-lines algorithms. When comparing the two methods, it is clear that the Extension of the Secant technique is more efficient and uses fewer iterations; in contrast, the Extension of the Newton-Raphson approach provides the best accuracy but requires more iterations. The fact that the Parallel approach did not converge for all functions demonstrated its limitations and highlighted the necessity of using several techniques to solve different types of equations. This research provided useful insights for optimizing numerical solutions in mathematics and computing contexts, and it highlighted the need to select root-finding methods based on the individual properties of the function.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors affirm that they have no conflicts of interest related to the work presented in this manuscript.

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